

Market Risk in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics Using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Literature Review

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the development of research around market risk in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions. The research was conducted from 1977 to 2022, by searching national and international journals indexed by Google Scholar, Sprott, and Scopus via the Perish/Harzing application, with the keyword "Market Risk". Based on the search results, there were 400 research articles, then inputted into the VOSviewer application and analyzed descriptively through a literature review study. The results showed that the number of publications had increased significantly every year. Furthermore, based on the results detected using the VOSviewer application, research related to market risk is divided into 6 clusters. Meanwhile, based on the results of a literature review study, there are 11 main themes related to market risk in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions.

Keywords: Market Risk, Bibliometrics, VOSviewer, Literature Review, Islamic and Conventional Banking

INTRODUCTION

Risk management in financial institutions has improved in line with developments in the financial industry as a whole. In recent years, financial institutions have begun to understand the importance of risk management to maintain business stability and continuity. This can be seen from the existence of regulations from the Financial Services Authority (OJK) which regulate risk exposure management and effective corporate governance. Risks in the financial sector must be recognized and controlled by estimating the potential that may occur in the future, not after the risk has already occurred. Therefore, a methodology for modeling risks that may occur in the future is very important so that those making decisions can prepare strategies to overcome future risks. One of the risks that occur in the financial industry is market risk. Market risk management involves identifying, assessing, controlling and monitoring these risks over time to ensure that the bank remains stable and maintains its reputation.

In previous research, the development of market risk in banking involved potential losses caused by changes in market conditions, such as fluctuations in securities prices, interest rate volatility, and economic crises. Banks must manage market risks well to ensure the stability and continuity of their business. Some of the efforts made include portfolio diversification, implementing an effective market risk model, and increasing transparency. Market risk is the risk that arises from price changes that occur in the market, such as changes in the value of shares, assets, currencies or commodities. Market risk can occur due to various factors, such as changes in economic policies, political conditions, geological and environmental situations, changes in interest rates, or changes in market trends. This affects the value of investment portfolios and forces investors to make difficult decisions. Therefore, it is very important for investors to understand and manage market risks properly. Commonly used strategies are portfolio diversification, limiting exposure to certain assets, and conducting regular market analysis to monitor changes and make smart investment decisions. There are 4 factors related to market risk, namely capital risk, return risk, commodity risk and currency risk. Therefore, because Islamic banks use products in the form of contracts, their market risk cannot be separated from the four standard market risk factors like conventional banks, even one financial product can have several types of contracts. The absence of interest at a sharia bank does not mean the bank is not exposed to interest risk. Islamic banks will also face the risk of pricing their products, which can be directly related to interest rates in the market.

Based on the problems above, it is necessary to map market risk management topics to identify, measure and control risks that will occur. This can fulfill the need for human resources tasked with risk management to have work attitudes, knowledge and skills according to the bank's needs. So, the aim of this research is to map research topics around market risk in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions using: (1) the VOSviewer bibliometric method to analyze and study maps of literature development in publications in a scientific field by creating a metadata network map; and (2) literature review study to analyze, identify and review articles from indexed international journals and accredited national journals.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Market risk is the risk that arises from price fluctuations of financial assets such as shares, bonds, currencies and commodities. This can affect the bank's financial performance and cause losses. Market risk in banking can occur due to various factors, such as changes in economic policies, changes in interest rates, political and geological conditions, or changes in market trends. Banks must properly manage market risks to ensure financial stability and maintain their reputation. The main objective of market risk management is to ensure financial stability and minimize potential losses caused by fluctuations in financial asset prices. This includes: (1) Identifying risks; (2) Limitation of losses; (3) Ensuring financial stability; (4) Improved reputation; and (5) Improved financial performance. Market risk refers to the possibility of loss or undesirable price fluctuations in one's investments or financial portfolio due to changes in global market conditions and macroeconomic factors. Market risk includes fluctuations in asset prices, such as stocks, bonds, commodities, and currencies, which are influenced by economic, political, and social events. Market risk can also be influenced by internal factors, such as poor management decisions, changes in market conditions, or a company's failure to respond quickly and appropriately to market changes. Individuals or companies involved in financial markets need to understand market risks and carry out appropriate risk management, such as portfolio diversification, use of derivative instruments, and other risk management strategies to reduce market risks and protect their investments from unwanted losses.

Bibliometric studies are research methods used to quantitatively analyze and measure scientific production and dissemination in published publications, be they scientific journals, books, or conference proceedings. Bibliometric studies collect data from literary sources to analyze the characteristics, trends, and influence of certain research or certain fields of science in a certain time and place. Bibliometric studies can provide information about the number and type of publications published in a discipline, the ranking or impact of a particular journal or book, collaborations between authors or institutions, and the citation patterns and influence of those publications. The results of bibliometric studies can help to identify trends and directions in a field of science, evaluate the quality of publications or contributions from certain researchers, and help make decisions in research or scientific development.

VOSviewer is bibliometric data analysis and visualization software developed by Nees Jan van Eck and Ludo Waltman of Delft University of Technology in the Netherlands. This software is used to analyze and visualize bibliometric data such as citations, publications, and collaborations between authors or institutions in a particular research field. VOSviewer can be used to analyze and visualize data in various forms, such as network graphs, heatmap diagrams, linkage maps, and topic classification. This software can help to understand structure and patterns in bibliometric data, identify trends in specific research areas, and generate new insights about the relationships between researchers, institutions, topics, and publications within a discipline. VOSviewer can also be used to integrate bibliometric data with other data, such as citation data, text data, or social media data. This software is widely used by researchers, bibliometricians and practitioners in various research fields to visualize bibliometric data and gain new insights into research dynamics and trends in specific disciplines.

literature review study is a research method that involves critical analysis and evaluation of literature or literature studies that are relevant to the research topic being carried out. The main purpose of a literature review study is to gain a better understanding of the research topic, review and evaluate conclusions that have been reached in previous research, and identify research gaps or research questions that still need to be answered. Literature review studies are usually carried out by searching databases, journals, books and other literature sources related to the research topic. After the relevant literature sources have been found, the researcher then carries out critical analysis and evaluation of the literature, such as evaluating research methodology, data collection, and interpretation of results. Literature review studies can be conducted as independent studies or as part of larger research. Literature review studies can help researchers to develop conceptual frameworks, design appropriate research methodologies, and identify research gaps in a particular field. Literature review studies can also help researchers gain a broader understanding of the research topic and provide a strong foundation for further research.

METHODOLOGY

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in literature review studies. The object of the research is market

risk. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles on market risk in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions.

The source of data collection comes from searching national and international journals indexed by Google Scholar, Sinta and Scopus via the Perish/Harzing application. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer software. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category with the key word "Market Risk " within the entire year period (1977-2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping research topics based on literature review studies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Market Risk in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions

There are 400 international and national journals based on the results of data collection from the Perish/Harzing application during the period 1977 to 2022. There are 313 international journals indexed by Scopus. And there are 87 international and national journals indexed by Sinta around market risk research.

Table 1. Journal publication data regarding Market Risk by year

Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications
1977-1998	34	2005	4	2011	10	2017	28
2000	3	2006	9	2012	10	2018	29
2001	2	2007	2	2013	18	2019	34
2002	6	2008	7	2014	21	2020	31
2003	7	2009	9	2015	16	2021	48
2004	3	2010	8	2016	16	2022	45

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Bibliometric Mapping of Research on Market Risk in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions

There are several things that need to be considered in knowing bibliometric results with VOSviewer software, namely: first, the software interface, namely the VOSviewer interface displays diagrams and graphs that visualize publication data. Users can open and explore these charts and graphs by clicking on specific items or zooming in on specific parts of the diagram. Second, visual components, namely several visual components that may appear in VOSviewer bibliometric results including nodes (representations of publications), lines (representations of citation relationships), and colors (representations of categories or topics). Third, citation network analysis, namely citation network analysis helps in determining relationships between publications and understanding how publications are related to each other. Larger nodes in the diagram represent more widely noted publications and relationships between nodes can help in understanding how publications are related. Fourth, cluster analysis, namely cluster analysis helps in determining relationships between topics or fields of science and understanding how publications are related to certain topics or fields of science. The colors in the diagram represent categories or topics and help in understanding how publications relate to different topics or fields of science. Fifth, citation analysis, namely citation analysis helps in determining the most noted publications and understanding how publications are related to each other. Larger nodes in the diagram represent more widely recorded publications and help in understanding how publications relate to each other. The results are as follows:

ensure the stability and continuity of the bank's business, so that the bank can continue to serve customer needs and fulfill their financial obligations. Several specific objectives of market risk management in banking include: (1) Preventing large losses; (2) Ensuring the continuity of the bank's business; (3) Maintain banking stability; (4) Maintain public trust; and (5) Maintain asset value.

Mapping Literature Review around Market Risk Supervision

There are 3 findings in research topics around operational risk monitoring, namely:

First, the authority and responsibilities of the Board of Commissioners, namely: (1) The Board of Commissioners is responsible for establishing market risk management policies and procedures in accordance with applicable industry regulations and standards; (2) The Board of Commissioners must ensure that market risk management policies and procedures have been implemented properly by bank management; (3) The Board of Commissioners must ensure that market risk management runs effectively and the results meet expectations and objectives; (4) The Board of Commissioners must ensure that the bank has an adequate internal control system to monitor and manage market risks; and (5) The Board of Commissioners must ensure that information about market risks within the bank is available and transparent to stakeholders.

Second, the authority and responsibilities of the Board of Directors, namely: (1) The Board of Directors must ensure that the bank's business strategy considers market risk and has a mechanism to manage it; (2) The Board of Directors must determine market risk limits for each bank business activity and ensure that business activities do not exceed these limits; (3) The Board of Directors must coordinate market risk management activities with other business activities within the bank; (4) The Board of Directors must ensure that the bank has an adequate internal control system to monitor and manage market risks; and (5) The Board of Directors must ensure that information about market risks within the bank is available and transparent to stakeholders.

Third, Human Resources / HR. HR plays an important role in managing market risk in banking. Human resources who have the right competencies and qualifications can help banks manage market risks effectively.

Fourth, Market Risk Management Organization. The Market Risk Management Organization is the part of the banking organization that is responsible for managing and controlling market risks faced by the bank. The goal is to ensure that the bank remains stable and maintains financial integrity despite market fluctuations. The Market Risk Management Organization must work effectively and integrated with other parts of the banking organization, such as Finance, Operations and Compliance, to ensure that market risks can be managed and controlled effectively.

Mapping Literature Review around Strategy, Risk Levels and Market Risk Limits

First, market risk management strategy. The findings in this research topic are that market risk management strategies in banking usually include several things such as: (1) Portfolio diversification, namely dividing investments into several types of assets that are not related to each other, so that risks are distributed and can be reduced; (2) Hedging, which is a strategy used to limit potential losses by buying or selling certain assets to offset price changes in other assets; (3) Position limitation, namely a strategy that determines limits on the amount of assets that can be accepted by the bank to manage market risk; (4) Stress testing, namely a simulation to assess how the bank will react to a worst-case scenario, such as unexpected changes in prices or interest rates; and (5) Liquidity management, namely a strategy to ensure that the bank has sufficient funds to meet short-term obligations and maintain financial stability.

Second, the level of market risk to be taken (Risk Appetite) and market risk tolerance (Risk Tolerance). Risk Appetite and Risk Tolerance are important concepts in making investment decisions. Risk Appetite refers to the amount of risk an investor or company is willing to take, while Risk Tolerance refers to the amount of risk a person or company can accept without affecting their financial stability. It helps investors or companies determine what they want from their investments and how they manage risk. In this case, investors or companies must consider factors such as age, financial goals, and level of financial stability when determining their Risk Appetite and Risk Tolerance.

Third, limits. Limits on market risk in banking are certain limits or measures applied by banks to limit or control market risks that may occur. This could be a limit on the amount invested in a particular instrument, a price fluctuation limit or an acceptable loss limit. This limit aims to ensure that the bank remains stable and has adequate reserves to overcome potential losses from market fluctuations. Banks can create limits as internal triggers to avoid reaching maximum limits, such as setting internal limits for Net Open Foreign Exchange

Position (PDN) to prevent exceeding the limits set by applicable regulations, especially when all internal limits have been used.

Mapping Literature Review around Market Risk Policies and Procedures

There are 4 findings in the research topic regarding operational risk policies and procedures in banking, namely:

First, the trading book and banking book policy, which is part of the market risk management policy in banking which regulates the criteria and mechanisms for managing financial instruments as part of the trading book and banking book. This policy must include the objectives of having positions in both books, valuation methodology, market risk measurement methods, and open position consolidation procedures.

Second, it is important to have unaffiliated parties perform regular testing and validation on market risk measurement models and pricing models to ensure their accuracy and robustness. An independent party with background and expertise in the area can provide an objective review and ensure that the model meets standards and best practices.

Third, determine and record trading strategies for each trading book position or portfolio. There are several mechanisms that can be used, including: (1) Systematic documentation; (2) Use of trading software; (3) Socialization and open discussion; and (4) Practice and testing.

Fourth, to determine the difference between reference interest rates or market interest rates, banks must have clear and transparent policies and processes. The following are some of the elements typically included in such policies and processes: (1) Market analysis; (2) Determination of reference interest rates; (3) Criteria and factors considered; (4) Internal control; and (5) Practice and testing

Mapping Literature Review around Market Risk Identification and Monitoring

First, identify market risks. The findings in this research topic are: (1) Portfolio analysis helps to identify the types of assets and liabilities owned by banks as well as the level of risk associated with each asset and liability; (2) Market data analysis including identifying trends and changes in prices of bank assets and liabilities, interest rates, and currency values; (3) Banks can use mathematical models to estimate the level of risk and potential losses associated with their portfolio; (4) Banks must identify fundamental sources of risk, such as global economic conditions, regulatory changes, and changes in the financial industry; (5) Banks must take into account various possible scenarios and estimate the level of risk and potential loss associated with each scenario; and (6) Banks must carry out regular monitoring and evaluation of market risks to ensure that the risk management strategies used are still effective and in accordance with changing market conditions.

Second, market risk monitoring, namely: (1) Banks must store relevant data and information regarding assets, liabilities and market risks, including market prices, interest rates and currency values; (2) Banks must monitor changes in prices and values of assets and liabilities as well as changes in interest rates and currency values periodically; (3) Banks must conduct risk analysis periodically to ensure that market risks can be identified and managed properly; (4) Banks must monitor risk management policies and strategies to ensure that they are appropriate to changing market conditions; (5) Banks must conduct regular internal audits to ensure that the risk management process is running well and meets applicable industry standards; and (6) Banks must ensure that reports and information regarding market risks are available and disseminated to relevant parties, such as directors, regulators and shareholders.

Mapping Literature Review around Market Risk Measurement

There are 7 findings in the research topic surrounding market risk measurement in banking, namely:

First, banks must have a system or model to measure market risk because market risk is one of the risks that must be considered in banking operations and policies. Market risk measurement models or systems enable banks to objectively measure and evaluate the level of risk associated with their financial position and operations. This enables banks to identify and understand market risks and make informed decisions regarding how these risks can be best managed.

Second, the market risk measurement system must include: (1) Value at Risk /VaR, measuring the amount of potential loss that may occur in an asset portfolio within a certain time period and with a certain level of confidence; (2) Scenario Analysis, namely scenario analysis measuring market risk by taking into account various market change scenarios, such as changes in interest rates or asset price fluctuations; (3) Stress Testing, which is a market risk measurement method that takes into account various extreme scenarios in the market, such as a financial crisis or economic recession, to measure potential losses that may occur in an asset

portfolio; (4) Monte Carlo Simulation, which is a market risk measurement method that uses simulation techniques to calculate various market change scenarios and estimate potential losses that may occur in asset portfolios; (5) Extreme Value Theory / EVT, which is a market risk measurement method that takes into account the potential for extreme events, such as market crashes or other major events, and estimates the potential losses that may occur in an asset portfolio.

Third, the measurement tool must be able to measure risk exposure that can be quantified, such as: (1) Market risk exposure in the trading book, namely the level of risk related to the financial position and transactions taken by a bank in its trading book. The trading book includes assets and financial positions taken by the bank to gain short-term profits and take advantage of market opportunities; (2) Measuring market risk exposure with Fair Value Option (FVO), namely the process of identifying and estimating the level of risk associated with the Fair Value Option (FVO) position held by the bank. FVO is an option that gives the holder the right to buy or sell an asset at the current market price or a predetermined price on the expiration date; and (3) Measuring market risk exposure using the banking book, namely the process of identifying and estimating the level of risk associated with positions and transactions in a bank's banking book. The banking book includes assets and financial positions taken by the bank to meet long-term obligations and meet customer needs.

Fourth, banks can use the gap report method, which is a method for measuring interest rate risk by estimating potential losses caused by changes in interest rates within a certain period of time. The gap report identifies the "gap" or gap between the interest rates on bank assets and liabilities and estimates the potential losses that may occur if interest rates change.

Fifth, banks can measure market risk in data-based banking using various methods, including: (1) Banks can analyze historical data to estimate future market risk; (2) Banks can use mathematical models to estimate market risk; (3) Banks can use stress testing to estimate how banking positions will be affected by extreme market risk scenarios; (4) Banks can also monitor market data in real-time to monitor market risks and make the right decisions at the right time.

Sixth, process of examining or validating the Market Risk measurement model, namely: (1) Model description; (2) Independent validation; (3) Validity test; (4) Robustness test; (5) Sensitivity analysis; and (6) Monitoring and evaluation.

Mapping Literature Review around Market Risk Control

There are 5 findings in research topics around market risk control, namely:

First, controlling market risk in banking to prevent large losses, namely: (1) Understanding the risk profile; (2) Setting risk limits; (3) Portfolio diversification; (4) Developing a risk monitoring system; (5) Carrying out stress testing; (6) Maintain data quality; and (7) Conduct periodic reviews.

Second, the implementing unit in banking has the responsibility to control market risk through the implementation and implementation of appropriate market risk control procedures and systems. They must ensure that banks have appropriate and accurate market risk measurement systems, and that these systems are regularly monitored and validated to ensure the accuracy and reliability of their measurement results. The implementation unit is also responsible for continuously monitoring and evaluating the level of banking market risk exposure and ensuring that risk control measures are taken immediately if necessary.

Third, banks that hold securities and bonds must carry out: (1) portfolio diversification; (2) Hedging; (3) Continuous market monitoring; (4) Setting risk limits; (5) Have an accurate market risk measurement system; and (6) Carrying out stress testing.

Fourth, for hedging transactions, by: (1) Banks can buy options or futures contracts to protect themselves from unfavorable price fluctuations in an asset; (2) Banks can carry out offsetting transactions to limit potential losses that may occur due to price fluctuations. For example, if a bank has a long position on an asset, they may initiate a sell transaction on a similar asset to limit potential losses; (3) Banks can purchase widely accepted products, such as stock indexes or bond indexes, to protect themselves from unfavorable price fluctuations in an asset; (4) Banks may spread their investments across different types of assets to reduce market risks associated with one type of investment; and (5) Banks must monitor market risks continuously and ensure that the hedging measures taken limit potential losses that may occur.

Mapping Literature Review regarding Internal Control of Market Risk

There are 4 findings in the research topic regarding internal control of market risk, namely: (1) Banks must have long-term plans and strategies to control market risk; (2) Banks must ensure that the information and data required to measure market risk are available and consolidated; (3) Banks must ensure that all staff

understand market risks and how to measure and address them; (4) Supervision and control system Banks must have an effective supervision and control system to ensure that market risks are properly controlled; and (5) Banks must continue to improve market risk control processes and systems to ensure that risks can be identified and controlled effectively.

Mapping Literature Review around Market Risk Management Information Systems

There are 2 findings in the research topic surrounding Market Risk Management Information Systems, namely:

First, the market risk management system in banking involves several main stages, namely: (1) Stage involving identification of sources of market risk, such as price changes, volatility and market liquidity; (2) The stage that involves evaluating the level of bank exposure to market risk and estimating potential losses that may occur; (3) A stage that involves continuous monitoring of market conditions and changes that may affect market risk exposure; (4) Stage involving the implementation of market risk management strategies, such as limiting exposure, portfolio diversification, and implementing hedging transactions; and (5) The stage that involves reporting market risks to interested parties and evaluating the performance of the market risk management system periodically to ensure its effectiveness and efficiency.

Second, the information risk management system is a system that helps banks identify, evaluate and control information risks that may occur. In the context of market risk, these systems should facilitate stress tests as part of the risk evaluation and control process. Stress tests are simulations that help banks understand how their portfolios or assets will react in extreme or unexpected market situations. This helps banks prepare and make plans to overcome potential losses that may occur during difficult market situations. Therefore, an information risk management system that facilitates stress tests is essential for banks in managing their market risks.

Mapping Literature Review around Determinants of Market Risk

There are 19 research topics surrounding the determinants of market risk in banking, namely:

(1) Accounting Risk. If there is accounting risk in banking, this can affect banking financial performance, which in turn can affect share prices and banking market value. Therefore, accounting risk can increase market risk in banking.

(2) Commodity Risk. Commodity risk is related to fluctuations in commodity prices which may have an impact on the performance of companies related to these commodities. If banking is related to the commodity industry, then price fluctuations can affect banking financial performance and in turn affect share prices and banking market value. Therefore, commodity risk can also increase market risk in banking.

(3) Covid-19. The Covid-19 pandemic has caused uncertainty in global financial markets and caused significant economic turmoil. Banks affected by the Covid-19 pandemic may experience a decline in financial performance and market value. In addition, market uncertainty can cause a decrease in investor confidence and increase market risk in banking.

(4) Certification. Diversification can help banking companies reduce market risk. By having a diversified portfolio, banking companies can reduce the risk of individual asset price movements related to market risk.

(5) Equity Risk. Equity risk refers to the risk arising from fluctuations in stock prices or the market value of equity assets. Equity risk can have an impact on market risk in banking companies. When the market value of a banking company's equity decreases, the market risk on the banking company also increases because investors may feel uncomfortable with large market fluctuations and increased risks.

(6) Company Size. Company size can influence market risk in banking companies. The larger the banking company, the greater the risk it may have to bear because the banking company will be affected by broader market conditions. However, larger banking companies may also have more resources and expertise to address market risks, and may benefit from broader portfolio diversification.

(7) Financial Leverage. Financial leverage refers to the use of borrowed funds to increase investment returns. Financial leverage can influence market risk in banking companies. The higher the financial leverage, the greater the market risk that the banking company must bear because banking companies have more financial obligations. If the market experiences sharp fluctuations, banking companies that have high financial leverage can experience greater losses.

(8) Foreign Currency Exchange Risk. Foreign currency exchange rate risk can influence market risk in banking companies because banking companies are usually involved in cross-border transactions and have

assets or liabilities linked to foreign currencies. If foreign currency exchange rates fluctuate sharply, then banking companies can experience large losses on their foreign currency positions.

(9) Stock Investment. Stock investments can affect market risk in banking companies because banking companies have investments in the stock market and can also be affected by share price fluctuations. If the value of shares declines significantly, the banking company could experience large losses in its stock investment portfolio, which in turn could affect the company's financial performance and market risk.

(10) Interest Rate Derivatives. Banking companies often use interest rate derivatives to reduce interest rate risk on the credit or bonds they own. However, interest rate derivatives can also influence market risk in banking companies. If the use of interest rate derivatives is not managed well or if the price of interest rate derivatives experiences sharp fluctuations, then banking companies can experience large losses in their interest rate derivative positions.

(11) Interest Rate Risk. Interest rate risk is related to fluctuations in interest rates which can affect the value of assets and liabilities of banking companies. If interest rates rise, the market value of banking company liabilities that have a fixed interest rate will fall, while the market value of assets with a fixed interest rate will rise. Conversely, if interest rates fall, the market value of banking company liabilities that have a fixed interest rate will rise, while the market value of assets with a fixed interest rate will fall. Interest rate risk can influence market risk in banking companies because interest rate fluctuations can affect the company's financial performance and the market value of the banking company's investment portfolio.

(12) Interbank Risk. Interbank risk is related to the possibility of banks experiencing difficulties in obtaining loans from other banks or in paying loans that have been received from other banks. Interbank risk can influence market risk in banking companies because banking companies can experience liquidity and financial pressure if it is difficult to obtain loans from other banks or if they have to pay loans at higher interest rates.

(13) Debt Ratio. A high debt ratio can affect market risk in banking companies because banking companies become more vulnerable to interest rate fluctuations and credit risk. If a banking company cannot pay back its debts, the banking company may experience financial pressure which can affect the company's financial performance and market value.

(14) Net Interest Margin / NIM. NIM can influence market risk in banking companies because low NIM can affect the financial performance of banking companies and the company's market value. If a banking company's NIM is low, the banking company will experience a decline in revenue and net profit, which in turn can affect the company's market value. Apart from that, a low NIM can also indicate that a banking company has high interest rate risk and is vulnerable to unexpected interest rate fluctuations.

(15) Non-Performing Loans /NPL. NPLs can affect market risk in banking companies because high NPLs can reduce banking company revenues and increase credit costs. If a banking company has a lot of non-performing loans, then the banking company must increase its loss reserves to anticipate the possibility of the borrower's failure to pay the loan. This can affect the financial performance of banking companies and the company's market value.

(16) Option Price Risk. Option Price Risk is related to the risk of market price fluctuations that can affect the assets and liabilities of banking companies. Price Risk Options can influence market risk in banking companies because banking companies can experience large losses if asset prices fall suddenly. Apart from that, price risk can also affect the financial performance of banking companies and the company's market value.

(17) Return On Assets /ROA. ROA can influence market risk in banking companies because a low ROA can indicate that a banking company is having difficulty generating profits from its assets. Low ROA can also affect the financial performance of banking companies and the company's market value, because investors may not be interested in banking companies that do not generate sufficient profits. Apart from that, a low ROA can also indicate that a banking company has high credit risk or is inefficient in managing its assets.

(18) Return On Equity /ROE. ROE can influence market risk in banking companies because a high ROE shows that a banking company is efficient in managing the capital it has, so that it can attract investor interest and increase the company's market value. However, a high ROE can also indicate that the banking company has high risk due to the use of high leverage or making investments that are too aggressive.

(19) Specific Risks. Specific risk can influence market risk in banking companies because if a banking company has high specific risk, then this can affect the company's financial performance and the company's market value. For example, if a banking company has management problems or is involved in a financial scandal, this can reduce investor confidence and affect the company's share price. Apart from that, specific

risks can also affect the operational performance of banking companies and the company's ability to face market risks.

Mapping Literature Review around the Influence of Market Risk

There are 20 research topics regarding the influence of market risk on banking, namely:

(1) **Abnormal Returns.** Market risk can influence abnormal returns (returns that cannot be explained by market factors) in banking. If there is a sharp decline in the stock market, the value of banking shares will also fall. This will cause negative abnormal returns. However, if banks are able to manage risk well, they can obtain positive abnormal returns when the stock market is stable or even increases.

(2) **Capital Structure.** Market risk can also affect banking capital structure. If there is a sharp decline in the stock market, banks may find it difficult to obtain funds through issuing shares. Instead, they may rely on loans from the central bank or other banks. This can affect banks' capital structure and increase their financial risks.

(3) **Cost of Equity Capital.** Market risk can also affect the cost of equity capital (cost of own capital) banking. If the stock market falls, then investors will be more likely to demand a higher rate of return to compensate for the higher risk. This will increase the cost of equity capital for banks. On the other hand, if the stock market is stable or even increases, then the cost of equity capital in banking can decrease.

(4) **Credit Risk.** Market risk can influence banking credit risk. If there is a sharp decline in the stock market, this can affect the financial condition of companies and consumers. As a result, banking credit risk may increase due to the impact of declines in asset values or consumers' ability to repay their debts. However, banking credit risk also depends on other factors such as the quality of the credit portfolio and effective credit risk management.

(5) **Dividend Policy.** Market risk can also influence banking dividend policies. If the stock market falls, banks may withhold dividend payments or even cut them to maintain liquidity and strengthen their capital position. Conversely, if the stock market is stable or even increasing, then banks may increase their dividend payments to share profits with their shareholders.

(6) **Return on Financing.** Market risk can also affect returns on banking financing. If the stock market falls, banks may face pressure to lower interest rates on their financing products to attract customers. On the other hand, if the stock market is stable or even increases, then banks may be able to increase interest rates on their financing products to maximize their returns.

(7) **Company Value.** Market risk has a big influence on the value of banking companies. Changes in market conditions such as fluctuations in interest rates, exchange rates, and market indices can affect a company's financial performance and, in turn, affect company value. When market risk increases, investors tend to value companies with higher risk and possibly estimate the value of the company lower. Conversely, when market risk decreases, investors may expect a higher company value.

(8) **Good Corporate Governance /GCG.** Market risk can also influence Good Corporate Governance (GCG) practices in banking companies. As market risks increase, banking companies may face pressure to generate higher profits in the short term. This can affect the company's GCG practices, such as transparency in financial reporting and good corporate governance. Conversely, when market risks decrease, companies tend to be able to focus more on GCG compliance and responsible practices.

(9) **Income Smoothing.** Market risk can also influence Income Smoothing practices in banking companies. As market risks increase, companies may feel pressure to produce more consistent and stable financial reports to maintain investor confidence. This can trigger the practice of income smoothing or earnings management which aims to smooth out profit fluctuations and demonstrate stable performance to investors. Conversely, when market risk decreases, companies tend to have more flexibility to publish financial reports that reflect actual market fluctuations.

(10) **Market Reaction.** Market risk can influence market reactions, where when uncertainty occurs in the market, the market will respond by selling or buying certain assets. This can cause asset price fluctuations and market volatility. In the banking sector, market reactions can have an impact on banking share prices.

(11) **Market Value.** Market risk can affect market value, where when significant market changes occur, this can affect banking financial performance and share prices. These changes can take the form of changes in demand and supply, interest rates, exchange rates, and other factors that influence banking performance.

(12) **Non-Performing Loans /NPL.** Market risk can also affect NPLs, where uncertainty in the market can affect the borrower's ability to repay the loan. When asset prices fall or interest rates rise, this can affect

borrowers' ability to repay their loans, which can lead to an increase in NPLs. Market risk can also affect the quality of bank assets, which can affect the bank's ability to obtain funding in the future.

(13) Price Ratio. Market risk can affect the Price Ratio of banking companies. The Price Ratio measures the share price of a banking company compared to the net profit generated. As market risk increases, investors tend to be more cautious in assessing the value of a company and choose to estimate a lower value of the company. This can cause a decrease in the company's share price and cause a decrease in the Price Ratio. Conversely, when market risk decreases, investors tend to be more confident in assessing the value of the company and may estimate the value of the company higher, thereby leading to an increase in the Price Ratio.

(14) Reputation Rating. Market risk can also affect the Reputation Rating of banking companies. When market risks increase, banking companies may experience a decline in financial performance and this can affect the public's perception and image of the company. Reputation Ratings are influenced by public perceptions of company performance and the level of public trust in the company. When market risk decreases and banking company performance improves, public perception and image of the company can improve and result in an increase in Reputation Rating.

(15) Return On Assets /ROA. Market risk can also affect the Return on Assets (ROA) of banking companies. ROA measures a company's effectiveness in using its assets to generate profits. As market risks increase, banking companies may experience pressure to generate higher profits and increase ROA in the short term. However, this can also increase the company's risk and can cause a decrease in ROA in the long term. Conversely, when market risk decreases, banking companies may be able to focus more on long-term strategies to increase ROA sustainably.

(16) Return On Equity /ROE. Market risk can affect the Return on Equity (ROE) of banking companies. ROE measures the net profit generated by a banking company compared to the equity it owns. As market risk increases, banking companies may experience a decline in ROE as investors will weigh the risk and expect higher returns. The banking company may then decide to lower dividends or shift resources to safer investments, thereby reducing ROE. Conversely, when market risk decreases, ROE can increase because investors are more inclined to take higher risks and earn higher returns.

(17) Stock Portfolio Diversification. Market risk can affect the diversification of banking company share portfolios. Stock portfolio diversification aims to reduce risk by spreading investment across several stocks with different risk profiles. As market risks increase, banking firms may tend to focus more on diversifying stock portfolios to reduce risk. However, in stable market conditions, banking firms may consider maintaining existing portfolios or adding higher-risk investments to increase potential returns.

(18) Share Price. Market risk can affect banking company share prices. Share prices reflect investors' expectations about the future performance of banking companies and can be influenced by changes in market risk. When market risk increases, banking company share prices tend to decrease because investors are more careful and consider greater risks. Conversely, when market risk decreases, banking company share prices can increase because investors are more confident and expect better performance.

(19) Stock Price Synchronicity. Market risk can influence the synchronicity of banking company share prices. Stock price synchronicity measures the extent to which shares of banking companies move together. When market risk increases, it is likely that all stocks in the market will be affected, thereby causing stock price synchronicity to increase. Conversely, when market risk decreases, shares of banking companies may move in a more independent manner, thereby causing share price synchronicity to decrease.

(20) Stock Profit Rate. Market risk can affect the level of profit on banking company shares. The stock profit rate is the ratio between a company's net profit and the number of shares outstanding. When market risks increase, banking companies may reduce dividends or even harm shareholders due to unstable economic conditions. This can cause stock profits to decrease. Conversely, when market risk decreases, banking companies may pay larger dividends or buy back shares, thereby increasing stock returns.

Mapping Literature Review regarding Market Risk Measurement Methods

There are 22 research topics regarding market risk measurement methods in banking, namely:

(1) Capital Asset Pricing Model /CAPM. This method takes into account market risk by using beta (beta coefficient) which measures an asset's sensitivity to market movements. The higher the beta, the greater the market risk the asset faces. By using CAPM, we can calculate the expected rate of return on an asset by taking into account the level of market risk.

(2) Capital, Asset, Management, Earning, Liquidity, Sensitivity to Market Risk /CAMELS. CAMELS takes six main factors that are considered important for evaluating a bank's financial health. These factors

include capital, assets, management, earnings, liquidity and sensitivity to market risk. Each factor is rated on a scale of 1-5, with a score of 1 indicating good performance and a score of 5 indicating poor performance. The total CAMELS score can provide an overview of the market risks faced by banks.

(3) Data Envelopment Analysis /DE A. DEA can be used to measure market risk by comparing a company's performance with the performance of other companies in the same industry. In DEA, each company is considered as an input and output variable that is entered into the model. DEA then calculates the relative efficiency of each company and assigns a score based on its performance relative to other companies in the same industry. Companies that have higher scores are considered to have lower market risk because they perform better compared to their competitors in the same industry.

(4) Expected Shortfall. This method takes into account the possibility of a loss that exceeds the VaR and how big the loss is. ES can provide more accurate information about market risk than VaR because VaR only takes into account the maximum loss that is possible at a certain level of confidence, while ES takes into account the average loss that is possible if an adverse event occurs.

(5) Exponential Weighted Moving Average /EWMA. This method gives higher weight to the latest data and lower weight to old data. In this way, EWMA can respond to changes in market volatility more quickly than a simple moving average method. This method is suitable for modeling asset price movements that have volatility that changes over time.

(6) Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroscedasticity /GARCH. Heteroscedasticity occurs when market volatility varies over time. The GARCH method models volatility as a function of previous volatility and other factors that can influence market volatility, such as interest rates and government policy. This method can provide more accurate volatility estimates than other methods when market volatility is unstable over time.

(7) Liquidity adjusted Value at Risk /LVaR. LVaR takes the VaR value as a basis and adjusts it to the liquidity level of the asset. This method takes into account the possibility that the asset cannot be sold easily in a liquid market and calculates the loss that may occur if the asset has to be sold at a price lower than the current market price.

(8) Markowitz Standard Deviation. This method takes the standard deviation value of the portfolio return as a measure of risk. Markowitz Standard Deviation takes into account the correlation between assets in a portfolio and gives higher weight to assets that have a lower correlation with other assets in the portfolio.

(9) Monte Carlo Simulation. This method takes into account various factors that can influence asset price movements, such as interest rates, market volatility, and other economic factors. In Monte Carlo Simulation, a mathematical model is used to generate a series of possible outcomes, which are used to estimate the level of market risk. This method can provide accurate risk estimates and is useful for taking into account various scenarios that may occur in the market.

(10) New Basel Minimum Capital Requirements. This method takes into account credit risk, market risk and operational risk. To measure market risk, this method uses a VaR value which is calculated based on asset price movements in the bank portfolio in a certain period. The calculated VaR is then used to determine the minimum amount of capital that must be maintained by the bank.

(11) Sensitivity to Market Risk. This method takes into account the risk generated by market fluctuations that are greater than previously expected. Sensitivity to Market Risk can help banks manage market risk by identifying assets that are most vulnerable to market fluctuations and adjusting portfolios in a timely manner.

(12) Stress Testing. This method takes into account various factors that can influence asset price movements, such as financial crises or significant changes in interest rates. In stress testing, financial institutions are tested in various scenarios and assessed for their ability to survive extreme situations. This method can help financial institutions identify market risks and take appropriate actions to reduce risks.

(13) Value at Risk / VaR. This method takes into account market volatility and correlation between assets in a portfolio to calculate losses that may occur in adverse market conditions. VaR provides a numerical value for market risk and can be used to determine the amount of capital required to protect a portfolio from unwanted losses.

(14) Stress testing explanations. Stress testing involves simulating different market scenarios to determine how much potential loss or risk there is to a portfolio or financial institution in such extreme situations. The goal of stress testing is to identify and measure market risks that are not detected by traditional methods such as VaR and ES.

(15) Stress testing results. Stress Testing Results are the results of market scenario simulations carried out in stress testing. These results measure the impact of extreme market situations on a portfolio or financial institution, including potential losses and risks. Stress testing results are used to evaluate the resilience and capital adequacy of a financial institution in facing extreme market situations.

(16) Market risk level of aggregation reported. Market Risk Level of Aggregation Reported is a way to report market risk at various levels of aggregation. At higher levels, market risk may be reported at the industry or sector level, while at lower levels, market risk may be reported at the individual asset level. The level of aggregation can influence how market risk is measured and managed, and can assist decision makers in identifying market risks associated with different levels of assets or portfolios.

(17) Back testing definition. Back Testing Definition is a method for testing the accuracy of a market risk model by comparing the results predicted by the model with actual results from past experience. In back testing, the model prediction results are tested by calculating VaR or ES at a certain time interval and comparing it with the actual losses that occurred in that time interval. The results of back testing are used to improve the model and increase the accuracy of market risk calculations.

(18) Average VAR. Average VAR is a method for measuring market risk by calculating the average of a number of VaRs. This method can be used to measure complex market risk, where a single VaR calculation may not provide an accurate picture of market risk. Average VAR can help measure market risk in portfolios that include many assets or in situations where market risk is unstable and volatile.

(19) Average ES. Average ES is a method for measuring market risk that is similar to Average VAR, but uses Expected Shortfall (ES) as a measure of market risk. Average ES calculates the average expected loss above a certain threshold value, within a certain time interval. This method can help measure complex market risk and provide a more accurate picture of market risk than VaR because ES considers the probability distribution of the entire expected loss, not just the maximum loss.

(20) Presence of graph about annual VAR fluctuations. A is a method for measuring market risk by visualizing fluctuations in VaR values over a certain period of time, such as over the course of a year. This graph can help companies see changing patterns of market risk and take the necessary actions to manage market risk.

(21) Limitations of VAR. Limitations of VAR include a lack of accounting for extreme risks and a reliance on assumptions that are not always met. VAR only calculates risk at a certain confidence level and does not consider the possibility of a loss greater than the VaR value. Additionally, VaR relies heavily on the historical data used to calculate it and cannot account for rapid and sudden changes in the market.

(22) Limitations of ES. Limitations of ES include reliance on the same assumptions as VaR and the need to use complex models to calculate it. Additionally, ES requires more historical data than VaR and can take longer to calculate, especially in complex portfolios. ES also has limitations in predicting extreme risks, although it is better than VaR in this regard.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows:

- The number of research publications regarding market risk in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions during the period 1977 to 2022 shows a significant increase from year to year. The total number of publications is 400 research articles, with 313 international journals indexed by Scopus, and there are 87 international and national journals indexed by Sinta.
- In the mapping visualization using the VOS viewer, the development of research regarding market risk in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions is divided into 6 clusters and 85 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 23 topics, cluster 2 consists of 18 topics, cluster 3 consists of 16 topics, cluster 4 consists of 13 topics, cluster 5 consists of 11 topics, and cluster 6 consists of 4 topics.
- Based on the literature review, there are 12 main themes of research regarding market risk in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions, namely: (1) Definition and objectives; (2) Risk monitoring; (3) Strategy, level of risk, limit; (4) Risk policies and procedures; (5) Risk identification and monitoring; (6) Risk measurement; (7) Risk control; (8) internal risk control; (9) Risk management information system; (10) Determinants of risk; (11) Influence of risk; and (12) Risk measurement methods.

It is recommended that further research use a larger data sample, so that it can explain a broader research mapping, considering the limitations of the data sample in this study and can add a longer research data time span so that the following research results can be obtained:

- It is hoped that the mapping results will show a higher and broader level of generalization.
- the literature review study can be explained in a more complex way.

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